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Methodological approaches to the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations in conditions of turbulence and risk

The subject of the research is to determine the main methodological approaches to the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations in the current conditions of turbulence and risk.

The aim of the research is to determine the methodological foundations, principles, impact of risks and turbulence on the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations.

Research methods. The following methods were used in the study: theoretical analysis; economic analysis; factor analysis; scenario analysis; risk management; case study; systematic; tabular, etc.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that transnational corporations (TNCs) are central to the modern global economy and their impact on the economic development of countries is

extremely large and powerful. However, the conditions of turbulence and risk pose obstacles to TNCs that require new methodological approaches to the formation and development of their economic potential. Methodological approaches to the development of TNCs' economic potential should take into account rapid changes in the external environment, which requires new management strategies, adaptation to conditions of instability and risk. The economic potential of transnational corporations is a set of material, financial, human, innovative, informational, managerial, production, technological and other resources that a company uses to ensure its sustainable development and increase its competitiveness in the global market. The main components of the economic potential of a TNC are: financial potential; innovation potential; human resources potential; and resource potential. The formation and development of TNCs' economic potential in the context of turbulence and risk are conditioned by the following factors: globalization and market integration; technological innovations; competition; political and economic risks; financial stability; demographic changes; socio-cultural factors; environmental requirements; adaptability and flexibility; cooperation and partnership. Besides, the formation and development of the economic potential of TNCs in the context of turbulence and risk requires compliance with a number of principles that allow TNCs not only to survive but also to develop in the face of uncertainty and risks that are characteristic of the modern global business environment. It is determined that the main methodological approaches are: risk diversification; flexibility of strategies; investment in innovation; effective management of human resources; adaptive planning; development of partnerships; implementation of sustainability principles.

Scope of the results. *Corporate economics, management of economic potential of enterprises, management of competitiveness of enterprises, risk management, enterprise security.*

Conclusions. *It has been established that in the context of global turbulence and risks, TNCs should adapt their approaches to the formation and development of economic potential, the ability to respond quickly to changes and the possibility of diversifying their risks. It is determined that the formation and development of TNCs' economic potential in the context of turbulence and risk is determined by certain factors, among which the main ones are: globalization and market integration; technological innovation; competition; political and economic risks; financial stability; demographic changes; socio-cultural factors; environmental requirements; adaptability and flexibility; cooperation and partnership. It is proved that these factors interact with each other, forming a unique context for each TNC in the current global environment. The main methodological approaches are proposed, namely: risk diversification; flexibility of strategies; investment in innovation; effective management of human resources. It is determined that strategic approaches, such as adaptive planning, development of partnerships and implementation of sustainability principles, provide TNCs with the opportunity to remain competitive and efficient in a constantly changing environment.*

Keywords: *transnational corporations, economic potential, turbulence and risks, efficiency, formation and development, methodological approaches, strategies, globalization, adaptation.*

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Методичні підходи до формування та розвитку економічного потенціалу транснаціональних корпорацій в умовах турбулентності та ризику

Предметом дослідження є визначення основних методичних підходів до формування та розвитку економічного потенціалу транснаціональних корпорацій в сучасних умовах турбулентності та ризику.

Метою дослідження є визначення методичних основ, принципів, впливу ризиків та турбулентності на формування та розвиток економічного потенціалу транснаціональних корпорацій.

Методи дослідження. В результаті дослідження були використані методи: теоретичного аналізу; економічного аналізу; факторний аналіз; сценарний аналіз; ризик-менеджменту; кейс-стаді; системний; табличний та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що транснаціональні корпорації (ТНК) займають центральне місце в сучасній глобальній економіці і їхній вплив на економічний розвиток країн надзвичайно великий та потужний. Однак умови турбулентності та ризику ставлять перед ТНК перешкоди, які вимагають нових методичних підходів до формування та розвитку їхнього економічного потенціалу. Методичні підходи до розвитку економічного потенціалу ТНК повинні враховувати швидкі зміни в зовнішньому середовищі, що вимагає нових стратегій управління, адаптації до умов нестабільності та ризику. Економічний потенціал транснаціональних корпорацій – це сукупність матеріальних, фінансових, людських, інноваційних, інформаційних, управлінських, виробничих, технологічних та інших ресурсів, які компанія використовує для забезпечення свого стійкого розвитку та підвищення конкурентоспроможності на глобальному ринку. Основними компонентами економічного потенціалу ТНК є: фінансовий потенціал; інноваційний потенціал; кадровий потенціал; ресурсний потенціал. Формування та розвиток економічного потенціалу ТНК в умовах турбулентності та ризику обумовлені такими чинниками: глобалізація та інтеграція ринків; технологічні інновації; конкуренція; політичні та економічні ризики; фінансова стабільність; демографічні зміни; соціально-культурні чинники; екологічні вимоги; адаптивність та гнучкість; співпраця та партнерство. Також формування та розвиток економічного потенціалу ТНК в умовах турбулентності та ризику вимагає дотримання ряду принципів, які дозволяють ТНК не тільки виживати, а й розвиватися в умовах невизначеності та ризиків, що є характерними для сучасного глобального бізнес-середовища. Визначено, що основними методичними підходами є: диверсифікація ризиків; гнучкість стратегій; інвестиції в інновації; ефективне управління кадровим потенціалом; адаптивне планування; розвиток партнерських відносин; впровадження принципів стійкості.

Галузь застосування результатів. Корпоративна економіка, управління економічним потенціалом підприємств, управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємств, ризик-менеджмент, безпека підприємства.

Висновки. Було встановлено, що в умовах глобальної турбулентності та ризиків ТНК мають адаптувати свої підходи до формування і розвитку економічного потенціалу, до здатності швидко реагувати на зміни і можливості диверсифікації своїх ризиків. Визначено, що формування та розвиток економічного потенціалу ТНК в умовах турбулентності та ризику обумовлюються певними чинниками, серед яких основними є: глобалізація та інтеграція ринків; технологічні інновації; конкуренція; політичні та економічні ризики; фінансова стабільність; демографічні зміни; соціально-культурні чинники; екологічні вимоги; адаптивність та гнучкість; співпраця та партнерство. Доведено, що ці чинники взаємодіють між собою, формуючи унікальний контекст для кожної ТНК в умовах сучасного глобального середовища. Запропоновано основні методичні підходи, а саме: диверсифікація ризиків; гнучкість стратегій; інвестиції в інновації; ефективне управління кадровим потенціалом. Визначено, що стратегічні підходи, такі як адаптивне планування, розвиток партнерських відносин та впровадження принципів стійкості, забезпечують ТНК можливість залишатися конкурентоспроможними та ефективними у постійно змінюваному середовищі.

Ключові слова: транснаціональні корпорації, економічний потенціал, турбулентність та ризики, ефективність, формування та розвиток, методичні підходи, стратегії, глобалізація, адаптація.

Formulation of the problem. Transnational corporations (TNCs) are central to today's global economy, and their influence on the economic development of countries is extremely large and powerful. However, the conditions of turbulence and risk, determined by globalization, changes in the political environment, technological shifts and other factors, pose obstacles to TNCs that require new methodological approaches to the formation and development of their economic potential. Since the modern economy is characterized by high uncertainty, frequent crises, political changes and economic fluctu-

ations, all this creates additional obstacles for TNCs in formulating their development strategy and managing risks. Methodological approaches to the development of TNCs' economic potential should take into account rapid changes in the external environment, which requires new management strategies, adaptation to conditions of instability and risk. TNCs should implement innovative solutions and new technologies, which requires the development of effective methods for their implementation. The study of the economic potential of TNCs is important not only in terms of their profits, but also in the context

of their impact on employment, environment and social responsibility, which are relevant topics on a global scale. Increased attention to environmental sustainability and corporate social responsibility also affects the development strategies of TNCs, as companies increasingly have to take into account the requirements of stakeholders for ethical and environmentally friendly business conduct. Thus, the study of methodological approaches to the formation and development of the economic potential of TNCs in conditions of turbulence and risk is necessary to ensure their sustainability, competitiveness and sustainable development.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The research of the problem of formation and development of the economic potential of TNCs in the context of turbulence and risk is an important aspect of modern economic science. Both Ukrainian and foreign authors are actively working on this topic, analyzing various aspects of strategy, management and adaptation of TNCs to changes in the global economy. Among domestic researchers, it is worth noting the following: O. G. Bilorus, who studied globalization processes and their impact on the development of TNCs, where he analyzed the impact of global economic turbulence on corporate strategies. V. M. Geyets – who studied global risks and their impact on the economic strategy of TNCs, as well as risk management issues in the context of turbulent economic changes. V. S. Savchuk – researched and analyzed methods of financial risk management and development of financial potential of TNCs. Yu. Kozak – studied the issues of integration processes and economic security of TNCs in the context of globalization and turbulence. Among foreign researchers on this topic, the most interesting are the works of the following scholars: M. Porter – a researcher of strategies of companies, including TNCs, who developed the concepts of competitive advantage and strategic approaches to work in conditions of turbulence. J. Dunning is the developer of the OLI model (Ownership, Location, Internalization), which analyzes the decisions of TNCs on asset allocation and risk management. S. Hymer is one of the first economists to pay attention to the nature and functioning of TNCs in the global economy and to study the issues of risks and economic barriers. J. Stiglitz – the author is known for his research on globalization and its implications for TNCs, in particular in the context of risks and turbulence. P. Dicken – analyzed glob-

al changes in the functioning of TNCs and their economic potential in the global economy. S. Ghoshal, who studied the strategies of international corporations, their development and adaptation to changes in the international environment, in particular under the influence of risks and instability. Thus, this issue has been studied by the scientific community of authors from many countries, but in order to study it in depth, there is a need for further research, analyzing various aspects from the impact of risks and turbulence on TNCs to the main methodological approaches to the formation of the economic potential of TNCs in conditions of turbulence.

Presenting main material. In today's globalized world, TNCs play a leading role in the development of the global economy. However, the growing uncertainty and turbulence in the markets caused by factors such as economic crises, wars, political instability, climate change and technological shifts are becoming significant obstacles for TNCs. In these conditions, the effective formation and development of the economic potential of corporations requires the development of new methodological approaches that take into account the dynamism of the external environment and the ability to adapt.

The economic potential of transnational corporations is a set of material, financial, human, innovative, informational, managerial, production, technological and other resources that a company uses to ensure its sustainable development and increase its competitiveness in the global market. The main components of economic potential are [1; 6; 8; 12; 15; 17; 21]:

- financial potential – the ability of TNCs to attract and distribute financial resources;
- innovation potential – the ability of TNCs to create and implement new technologies and products
- human resources potential – the level of qualification of employees and management potential of TNCs;
- resource potential – the ability to access natural and material resources of TNCs.

The formation and effective management of these components in the face of risks and turbulence is becoming a key task for ensuring the sustainable development of TNCs.

Risks and turbulence in the modern economic environment may have different nature, but their impact on TNCs is always significant (Table 1) [2; 3; 5; 9; 11; 14; 18]:

Table 1. The impact of risks and turbulence on TNCs in the current environment

Risks	Manifestation of turbulence
Economic	Cyclical fluctuations in the global economy, changes in exchange rates, inflationary processes
Political	Instability in certain regions, sanctions, nationalization or changes in regulatory policies in different countries
Social	Changes in consumer sentiment, social unrest, income inequality
Environmental	Climate change, natural disasters, toughening environmental regulations
Technological	Technological advances, cyber-attacks, rapid obsolescence of technologies

The turbulent environment requires TNCs to adopt adaptive strategies, the ability to respond quickly to changes, and the ability to diversify their risks. Accordingly, the formation and development of the economic potential of TNCs in conditions of turbulence and risk are conditioned by the following factors:

- globalization and integration of markets – interconnection between countries, which leads to the expansion of sales markets and reduction of production costs;
- technological innovations – development of new technologies, which allows to increase productivity, reduce costs and create new products and services;
- competition – increased competition both at the international and national levels requires TNCs to constantly improve and adapt;

- political and economic risks – instability of the political situation, changes in legislation, economic crises have a negative impact on the activities of TNCs;
- financial stability – access to financial resources, investment opportunities and crediting determine the ability of corporations to implement their strategies;
- demographic changes – changes in the structure of the population, the level of education and qualifications of employees affect the human resources of TNCs;
- socio-cultural factors – cultural differences, consumer preferences and social trends affect marketing and product development strategies;
- environmental requirements – the growing emphasis on sustainable development and environmental responsibility requires TNCs to implement new environmental standards;

Table 2. Principles of formation and development of TNCs' economic potential in turbulent conditions

Principle	Characteristics
Flexibility and adaptability	TNCs should be prepared to respond quickly to changes in market conditions, political situation and technological environment, which involves adapting business models, product portfolios and management strategies
Diversification	Diversification of markets, products and technologies reduces risks and helps to stabilize revenues, so TNCs can expand into new markets and offer new products to reduce dependence on individual segments
Innovation	Investing in research and development is critical to maintaining competitiveness, so innovation can help develop new products and services, as well as improve process efficiency
Partnership and collaboration	Strategic alliances and partnerships allow TNCs to gain access to new technologies, markets and resources. Collaboration with local enterprises can also reduce the risks of entering new markets
Risk management	Developing a risk management system, including risk identification, analysis and monitoring, is an important element of strategic management that helps TNCs respond to threats in a timely manner and reduce their impact
Social responsibility and sustainable development	Implementation of the principles of sustainable development and social responsibility can improve the reputation of TNCs, strengthen ties with local communities and reduce risks related to environmental and social aspects
Digitalization and technological innovation	Implementation of new technologies and digital solutions can improve operational efficiency, reduce costs and provide access to new markets
Analytics and monitoring	Using analytical tools to assess market conditions and consumer demand helps TNCs make informed decisions and adapt strategies in real time

- adaptability and flexibility – implies the ability of TNCs to quickly adapt to changes in the external environment and adjust their strategies;

- cooperation and partnership – interaction with other companies, government agencies, and research organizations has a positive impact on the development of technologies and entry into new markets.

These factors interact with each other to form a unique context for each TNC in the current global environment [4; 7; 10; 13; 16; 19].

The formation and development of the economic potential of TNCs in the context of turbulence and risk requires compliance with a number of principles (Table 2):

Adherence to these principles allows TNCs not only to survive, but also to develop in the face of uncertainty and risks that are characteristic of the modern global business environment. In the context of turbulence, it is necessary to develop methodological approaches to the formation of the economic potential of TNCs that will allow them to maintain stability and competitiveness in the global market. Among the main methodological approaches, we propose the following (Fig. 1) [4; 8; 17; 20; 22; 23].

One of the key methodological approaches is diversification at both the market and product levels. Diversification of the geographical location of production facilities and sales markets helps to reduce the impact of regional economic or political crises. In addition, product diversity, which allows TNCs to operate in different sectors of the economy, helps to reduce dependence on one type of product or service. TNCs should be able to quickly change their strate-

gies depending on changes in the external environment. Flexibility implies the ability to quickly switch between markets, customer segments, or technologies, which helps to avoid significant losses in the event of a crisis. Developing the innovative potential of TNCs is essential to maintain their competitiveness in the face of turbulence. Investments in new technologies, digital transformation, research and development allow corporations to develop new products and improve the efficiency of operational processes. In the face of constant change, highly qualified personnel capable of ensuring the company's adaptation to new conditions are becoming a key resource for TNCs. Investing in training, skills development and human resources management should be one of the priorities of corporations, where an important component is also the formation of a global corporate culture that takes into account the diversity of cultural and national characteristics [8; 13; 17; 20; 22].

Traditional strategic planning based on long-term forecasts is becoming less effective in the face of unpredictable changes in the markets. In such circumstances, adaptive planning models that allow TNCs to respond quickly to changes are becoming increasingly relevant. The main principles of adaptive planning are constant monitoring of the environment, flexibility in decision-making and the ability to quickly revise plans. Increasing sustainability and focusing on sustainable development are critical for TNCs seeking to reduce the impact of risks associated with environmental and social factors. Implementation of ESG principles (environmental, social and corporate governance) is becoming an impor-

Fig. 1. Methodological approaches to the formation of the economic potential of TNCs in turbulent conditions

tant part of corporate strategy, as it helps to reduce dependence on external risk factors and increase investor confidence [8; 10; 16; 19].

Strategic alliances with other companies, governments, or academic institutions are also of particular importance, allowing TNCs to use available resources more efficiently, reduce risks, and generate synergies. Partnerships can provide access to new markets, technologies, or financial resources, which helps to reduce the vulnerability of corporations in times of turbulence [6; 13; 17; 21]

Conclusions

Therefore, in the context of global turbulence and risks, TNCs must adapt their approaches to the formation and development of economic potential, the ability to respond quickly to changes and the possibility of diversifying their risks. The formation and development of TNCs' economic potential in the context of turbulence and risk are determined by certain factors, among which the main ones are: globalization and market integration; technological innovations; competition; political and economic risks; financial stability; demographic changes; socio-cultural factors; environmental requirements; adaptability and flexibility; cooperation and partnership. These factors interact with each other to form a unique context for each TNC in the current global environment. Accordingly, the main methodological approaches are risk diversification, strategy flexibility, investment in innovation, and effective human resource management. Strategic approaches, such as adaptive planning, development of partnerships and implementation of sustainability principles, provide TNCs with the opportunity to remain competitive and efficient in a constantly changing environment.

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СЕМЕНОВ О.С.

Координація монетарної та фіскальної політики в Україні з метою післявоєнного відновлення економіки

Предметом дослідження є рівень координації між монетарною та фіскальною політиками в Україні, що впливає на здатність країни забезпечувати макроекономічну стабільність.

Метою статті є дослідження напрямів підвищення координації між фіскальною та монетарною політиками України в умовах воєнного стану й поствоєнного відновлення.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані системний підхід, метод теоретичного узагальнен-